

Variation of Diffusion Coefficient of Strong Electrolytes according to Cube-root and First Power of Concentration

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It has been shown in previous publications that the expression for κ (Kappa) in the Debye-Hückel theory of strong electrolytes requires modification. The modified kappa, denoted by κ_m includes the 'effective ionic diameter', a within it and at constant a , its variation with the electrolyte concentration should follow the cube-root relationship.

Introducing this κ_m , and the effect of ionic hydration on activity coefficient into the thermodynamic part of the equation of Onsager and Fuoss, equations have been deduced for the diffusion coefficient D , containing terms involving cube-root and first power of C , the concentration. The equations have been subjected to test using the data available in the literature on a few 1:1 and 2:1 electrolytes and have been found satisfactory upto a concentration of 0.1 M .

ONsager and Fuoss¹ and later Hermans¹ have developed the theory of diffusion of strong electrolytes. Hermans² tested the validity of his equations using data on measurements of liquid junction potentials. The equations of Onsager and Fuoss have been subjected to extensive test by Harned and coworkers³⁻⁵. The data of these and other workers have been utilised by the author to test the validity or otherwise of the equations deduced by him by introducing a modified expression for κ (kappa) of the Debye-Hückel theory of strong electrolytes and the effect of ionic hydration into the thermodynamic part of the Onsager and Fuoss equation for the diffusion coefficient, D of the strong electrolytes yielding two kinds of ions only in solution. Mention may be made here that by using the modified kappa, equations have been deduced which agree well with literature data on ionic conductance and mean ionic activity coefficient of the strong electrolytes^{6,10,17}.

The equation of Onsager and Fuoss may be written as

$$D = 1000 RT (\nu_1 + \nu_2) \left(1 + C \frac{\partial \ln Y}{\partial C} \right) \frac{\bar{M}}{C} \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), RT has its usual significance, ν_1 and ν_2 represent the number of each one of the two kinds of ions per molecule of the electrolyte of molar concentration C , Y the mean activity coefficient and

$$\frac{\bar{M}}{C} = 1.0741 \times 10^{-20} \frac{\lambda_1^0 \lambda_2^0}{\nu_1 |Z_1| \Delta^0} + \Delta \bar{M}_1 / C + \Delta \bar{M}_2 / C \quad (1a)$$

where, Δ^0 and λ_1^0 and λ_2^0 denote respectively the equivalent conductance of the electrolyte and that

of the ions of two kinds at infinite dilution and $\Delta \bar{M}_1$ and $\Delta \bar{M}_2$ are the first and second order electrophoretic effects. It may be noted that $\Delta \bar{M}_1$ and $\Delta \bar{M}_2$ are of opposite sign and $\Delta \bar{M}_2 < \Delta \bar{M}_1$ and may be neglected. The expression for $\Delta \bar{M}_1 / C$ is as follows,

$$-\Delta \bar{M}_1 / C = \frac{(|Z_2| \lambda_1^0 - |Z_1| \lambda_2^0)^2}{(\Delta^0)^2 |Z_1 Z_2| (\nu_1 + \nu_2)} \times \frac{3.132 \times 10^{-10}}{\eta_0 (DT)^{1/2}} \times \frac{\sqrt{\Sigma C_i Z_i^2}}{(1 + \kappa a)} \quad (1b)$$

where, $|Z|$ represents the magnitude of valency, η_0 the viscosity and D the dielectric constant of the solvent. Harned and coworkers³⁻⁵ and Harned and Owen⁶ have used the Debye-Hückel expression for $\ln Y$ and their expression for the thermodynamic part of equation (1) may be written as follows,

$$\left(1 + C \frac{\partial \ln Y}{\partial C} \right) = 1 - \frac{1.1514 \times S_f \sqrt{C}}{(1 + A' \sqrt{C})^2} + 2.303 BC - C \psi(d) \quad (1c)$$

where, $S_f = 0.5091 \times \frac{1}{\nu \sqrt{2}} (\Sigma \nu_i Z_i^2)^{1/2}$, A' and B are constants and $\psi(d)$ is a function of the density term.

Substituting the aforesaid expression for the thermodynamic part in equation (1), simplifying and neglecting terms containing C (since C approaches zero) the following limiting equation is obtained,

$$D = D_0 - S_D \sqrt{C} \quad (LL)$$

where, $D_0 = 8.936 \times 10^{-10} \Gamma \left(\frac{\nu_1 + \nu_2}{\nu_1 |Z_1|} \right) \left(\frac{\lambda_1^0 \lambda_2^0}{\Delta^0} \right)$ (1d)

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$$\text{and } S_D = \frac{1.3273 \times 10^{-8}}{D^{3/2} T^{1/2}} \left(\frac{\sum \nu_i Z_i^2}{\nu_+ |Z_1|} \right)^{3/2} \left(\frac{\lambda_1^0 \lambda_2^0}{\Delta^0} \right) + \frac{2.604 \times 10^{-8}}{\eta_0 D^{1/2} T^{-1/2}} \left(\frac{\sum \nu_i Z_i^2}{|Z_1 Z_2|} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{|\lambda_1^0 - |Z_1| \lambda_2^0|}{\Delta^0} \right)^2 \quad (1e)$$

In equations (1d) and (1e), Z_1 and λ_1^0 refer to the positively charged ion and Z_2 and λ_2^0 refer to the negative ion of the electrolyte.

Modification introduced into equation (1) :

In the thermodynamic part of equation (1) following Glueckauf⁷ and Robinson and Stokes⁸ we may write,

$$\ln Y = \ln Y_s + \ln Y_{e_i} \quad (2)$$

where, (a) $\ln Y_s$ accounts for the effect of hydration of the ions (causing decrease in entropy) and (b) $\ln Y_{e_i}$ that of interionic attraction.

(a) Using volume fraction statistics, as has been done by Glueckauf⁷, we may write neglecting minor terms as follows,

$$\ln Y_s = \frac{0.018 \text{ m r} (r+h-\nu)}{(1+0.018 \text{ m r})^\nu} + \frac{h-\nu}{\nu} \ln(1+0.018 \text{ m r}) - \frac{h}{\nu} \ln(1-0.018 \text{ m h}) \quad (2a)$$

$$= \frac{0.018 \text{ m} (r^2+rh-r\nu)}{\nu} + \frac{h-\nu}{\nu} (0.018 \text{ m r})$$

$$+ \frac{h}{\nu} (0.018 \text{ m h}), \text{ approximately for } m=0.1 \text{ or}$$

less than 0.1,

$$= \frac{0.018 \text{ m}}{\nu} [r^2 + (h-\nu)(2r) + h^2] = B'C \quad (2b)$$

where†, $m=C$ for dilute solutions and

$$B' = \frac{0.018}{\nu} [r^2 + (h-\nu)(2r) + h^2].$$

In equation (2a), h and r represent hydration number and volume fraction, respectively.

(b) Replacing κ_m in place of κ we may write as follows,

$$\ln Y_{e_i} = - \frac{N e^2}{DRT} \left[\frac{\nu_+ Z_+^2 + \nu_- Z_-^2}{\nu_+ + \nu_-} \right] \kappa_m \quad (2c)$$

where, N is the Avogadro number and

$$\kappa_m = \left[\frac{4\pi e^2 \sum n_i Z_i^2 (f_o/f)}{D \kappa T} \right]^{1/2} \quad (2d)$$

where, f and f_o represent the mean activity coefficient of the ions inside and outside, respectively of the ion-atmosphere surrounding the central ion.

In previous publications^{9,10}, the expression for κ_m has been deduced by introducing the mean activity coefficient of the ions into the Boltzmann distribution formula. The same expression for κ_m may also be deduced in the following way.

† For dilute solutions it is assumed that $\ln \gamma = \ln Y$, where γ and Y represent the mean activity coefficient of the ions in molal and molar concentrations, respectively.

For simplicity, a 1 : 1 strong electrolyte solution is considered as reasoning developed for this type can be extended to other types of strong electrolytes also.

The chemical potential μ , of the ions within the ion-atmosphere of a central positively charged ion at a point, distant r from it, may be written as

$$\mu_1 = \mu_o + RT \ln (n_+)(n_-)f^2 \quad (i)$$

where, n_+ and n_- represent the number of positive and negative ions per unit volume and f their mean activity coefficient. In the bulk of the solution at a point outside the ion-atmosphere, where the electrical potential due to the central ion is zero, we may use for the chemical potential of the ions the following expression,

$$\mu_2 = \mu_o + RT \ln (nf_o)^2 \quad (ii)$$

where, n represents the number of positive or negative ions per unit volume (since $n_+ = n_-$) and f_o their mean activity coefficient. As the system is in equilibrium† so $\mu_1 = \mu_2$ and consequently

$$RT \ln (n_+)(n_-)f^2 = RT \ln (nf_o)^2 \quad (iii)$$

From equation (iii) the following equation is derived,

$$\frac{\kappa T}{e} \ln (n_+ f / nf_o) = \frac{\kappa T}{e} \ln (nf_o / n_- f) = - \frac{\kappa T}{e} \ln (n_- f / nf_o) = -\psi \quad (iv)$$

where, ψ represents the potential difference between the two points under consideration and κ , T and e have their usual significance.

It follows from equation (iv) that

$$n_- = n(f_o/f) \exp(e\psi/\kappa T) \quad (v)$$

$$\text{and } n_+ = n(f_o/f) \exp(-e\psi/\kappa T) \quad (vi)$$

Therefore, assuming linear approximation, the following expression is found for the density of charge ρ ,

$$\rho = -2 ne(f_o/f) e\psi/\kappa T \quad (vii)$$

By applying Poisson's equation we get,

$$\Delta^2 \psi = -4\pi \rho / D = \frac{4\pi e^2 2n}{D \kappa T} (f_o/f) \psi = \kappa_m^2 \psi \quad (viii)$$

$$\text{where, } \kappa_m = \left(\frac{4\pi e^2}{D \kappa T} \cdot 2n \right)^{1/2} (f_o/f)^{1/2} \quad (ix)$$

Thus the same expression for κ_m can be found by two different methods. Putting $(n_+)(n_-) = (n')^2$, it follows from equation (iii) that $(f_o/f) = (n'/n)$.

Let L denote the average distance between two neighbouring ions, hence, $\left(\frac{1}{2n}\right)^{1/3} = L = 2\pi a x \quad (x)$

where, a represents the 'effective ionic diameter' or the closest distance of approach between two

† It may be noted that Donnan's equation for membrane equilibrium, $(n_- f)(n_+ f) = (nf)^2$ follows directly from equation (iii) and when $f_o = f = 1$ (unity), equations (v) and (vi) lead to Boltzmann distribution law.

oppositely charged ions, and x , a dimensionless variable.

It follows from equation (x) that $(1/2\pi ax)^{1/2} = (2n)^{1/6}$. Substituting $(1/2\pi ax)^{1/2}$ for $(2n)^{1/6}$ and (n'/n) for (f_0/f) in equation (ix) and simplifying we get,

$$\kappa_m = \left[\frac{2e^2}{D\kappa T a} \right]^{1/2} \left[\frac{n'/n}{x} \right]^{1/2} (2n)^{1/3} \quad (\text{xi})$$

As n in equation (xi) increases, (n'/n) and also x diminish. Hence, it is assumed that over a certain range of values of n the ratio $(n'/n)/x$ remains constant. Therefore, for a certain value of n in the specified range, adjusting a and x in such a way that x is equal to n'/n , we may express equation (xi) as

$$\kappa_m = \left[\frac{2e^2}{D\kappa T a} \right]^{1/2} (2n)^{1/3} \quad (3)$$

$$= \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{a}} (\beta) [C^{1/3} - C_0^{1/3}] \quad (3a)$$

where, α and β are constants which can be calculated from theory and C_0 is a constant such that when $C=C_0$, κ_m becomes zero. C_0 is very small.

It follows from equation (3a) that so long as a , the effective ionic diameter, remains constant, κ_m varies as $C^{1/3}$.

Combining equations (2c) and (3) we get,*

$$\ln Y_{\theta,1} = - \frac{Ne^2 W}{2DRT} \left[\frac{2e^2}{D\kappa T a} \right]^{1/2} (2n)^{1/3} \quad (3b)$$

where, $W = (\nu_+ Z_+^2 + \nu_- Z_-^2) / (\nu_+ + \nu_-)$

The expressions for $\ln Y_{\theta,1}$, $\ln Y_{\theta}$ and $\bar{m}/C$ are now substituted in equation (1) which after differentiation, simplification and neglecting terms beyond the first power of C , yields the following equation for the diffusion coefficient,

$$D = D_0 - (\alpha/\sqrt{a})S(C^{1/3} - C_0^{1/3}) + BC \quad (4)$$

D_0 of equation (4) is identical with D_0 of equation (LL), α is equal to 1.22 for 1:1 electrolytes and for 2:1 electrolytes it is 1.14, and a represents the effective ionic diameter ($\text{\AA}$). It is to be noted

that $(\alpha/\sqrt{a}) = (\kappa_m/C^{1/3}) / (\kappa/C^{1/2})$

$$S = 8.849 \times 10^{-4} \frac{(\sum \nu_i Z_i^2)^{3/2}}{\nu_+ |Z_+| \nu_- |Z_-|} \left(\frac{\lambda_1^0 \lambda_2^0}{\Delta^0} \right) + \left(\frac{2.604 \times 10^{-8}}{\eta_0 D^{1/2} T^{-1/2}} \right) \frac{(\sum \nu_i Z_i^2)^{1/2}}{|Z_+ Z_-|} \left(\frac{|Z_+ \lambda_1^0 - |Z_- \lambda_2^0|}{\Delta^0} \right)^2$$

$$\text{and } B = B'D_0 = \left(\frac{0.018 D_0}{\nu} \right) [r^2 + 2r(h - \nu) + h^2] \quad (4a)$$

Equation (4) derived by modifying the thermodynamic part of equation (1) by the author, is subjected to test using the data recorded in Tables 1-4.

Processing of the data and verification of equation (4) :

Approximate values of $(\alpha/\sqrt{a})S$ and $(C_0)^{1/3}$ are first found by plotting graphically $(D - BC)$ against $(C)^{1/3}$ using the calculated or appropriate value of B . These approximate values are then improved by trial until the desired agreement between the observed and the calculated values of D is obtained.

Under the head miscellaneous in Tables, are mentioned the electrolyte selected, reference of the source of data, the equation and the values of the constants in it. In these Tables, C represents molar concentration. In column 5 of Table 2, the reference of the authors who used equation (1) in combination with the equations (1a) to (1c) has also been recorded. Harned and coworkers⁸⁻⁵ have used for $\ln Y$ in equation (1) the Debye-Hückel expression as represented by equation (1c). The symbols α , a and S used in Table 3 have the same significance as in equation (4). The electrophoretic effect has been taken into account in estimating S for LiCl and NaCl only, and not for the others. In Table 4, D_0 has its usual significance and h and r denote respectively the hydration number and volume fraction (*i.e.* the ratio of the apparent mole volume of the electrolyte at $C=1M$ to the mole volume 18 cm³ of water at 25°). The values of h for the four 1:1 electrolytes have been collected from a previous publication¹⁵ of the author and

TABLE 1—D OBSERVED AND CALCULATED BY EQUATIONS (4) AND (LL) AT 25°

Miscellaneous	C	Values of $D \times 10^6$		
		Obs.	Calcd. Eqn. (4)	Calcd. Eqn. (LL)
NaCl ^a Eqn. (4), $D_0 = 1.611 \times 10^{-5}$ $(\alpha/\sqrt{a})S = 0.36 \times 10^{-5}$ $(C_0)^{1/3} = 0.026$ $B = 0.30 \times 10^{-5}$ Eqn. (LL), $D_0 = 1.611 \times 10^{-5}$ $S_D = 0.98 \times 10^{-5}$	0.001	1.585	1.585	1.580
	0.002	1.574	1.576	1.567
	0.005	1.559	1.560	1.542
	0.01	1.545	1.546	1.513
	0.02	1.530	1.529	
	0.05	1.507	1.503	
0.10	1.482	1.483		
KCl ^b Eqn. (4), $D_0 = 1.994 \times 10^{-5}$ $(\alpha/\sqrt{a})S = 0.41 \times 10^{-5}$ $(C_0)^{1/3} = 0.022$ $B = 0.26 \times 10^{-5}$ Eqn. (LL), $D_0 = 1.994 \times 10^{-5}$ $S_D = 1.17 \times 10^{-5}$	0.001	1.962	1.962	1.957
	0.002	1.951	1.952	1.942
	0.005	1.933	1.934	1.911
	0.01	1.915	1.917	1.877
	0.02	1.892	1.897	
	0.05	1.866	1.865	
0.10	1.842	1.839		
CsCl ^c Eqn. (4), $D_0 = 2.044 \times 10^{-5}$ $(\alpha/\sqrt{a})S = 0.47 \times 10^{-5}$ $(C_0)^{1/3} = 0.024$ $B = 0.23 \times 10^{-5}$ Eqn. (LL), $D_0 = 2.044 \times 10^{-5}$ $S_D = 1.30 \times 10^{-5}$	0.001	2.009	2.009	2.006
	0.002	1.995	1.995	1.990
	0.005	1.975	1.976	1.959
	0.01	1.954	1.956	1.924
	0.02	1.930	1.933	
	0.05	1.892	1.894	
0.10	1.870	1.860		
BaCl ₂ ^a Eqn. (4), $D_0 = 1.386 \times 10^{-5}$ $(\alpha/\sqrt{a})S = 0.73 \times 10^{-5}$ $(C_0)^{1/3} = 0$ $B = 1.14 \times 10^{-5}$ Eqn. (LL), $D_0 = 1.386 \times 10^{-5}$ $S_D = 2.94 \times 10^{-5}$	0.001	1.317	1.314	1.294
	0.002	1.298	1.296	1.255
	0.005	1.263	1.267	1.178
	0.01	1.238	1.240	1.092
	0.02	1.212	1.211	
	0.05	1.176	1.174	
0.10	1.160	1.160		

* In a previous publication¹⁷ it has been shown that equation (3b) agrees well with the experimental data.

^aRefs. 6 and 11. ^bRefs. 6 and 12. ^cRefs. 6 and 12.

TABLE 2—D OBSERVED AND CALCULATED BY EQUATIONS (4), AND (1) TO (1c) COMBINED AT 25°

Miscellaneous	C	Values of D × 10 ⁵		
		Obs.	Calcd.	Cal'd. ^c
		Eqn. (4)	Eqn. (1) to (1c)	
LiCl ^a	0.00063	1.348	1.349	1.348
	0.00179	1.331	1.337	1.338
Eqn. (4), D ₀ = 1.367 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.00229	1.335	1.334	1.334
	0.00235	1.335	1.332	1.334
(κ/√a)S = 0.32 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.00339	1.327	1.328	1.328
	0.00496	1.326	1.322	1.322
(C ₀) ^{1/2} = 0.024	0.00568	1.319	1.320	1.320
	0.00732	1.320	1.316	1.316
B = 0.46 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.00834	1.313	1.314	1.314
Eqns. (1) to (1c) combined	0.00935	1.312	1.312	1.312
	0.0110	1.312	1.309	1.309
D ₀ = 1.367 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.050	1.280	1.280	—
S _D = 0.89 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.10	1.269	1.274	—
CaCl ₂ ^b	0.0017	1.251	1.247	1.253
	0.0021	1.236	1.242	1.248
Eqn. (4), D ₀ = 1.335 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.0032	1.227	1.228	1.236
	0.0043	1.214	1.218	1.227
(κ/√a)S = 0.76 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.0054	1.209	1.210	1.239
	0.0070	1.200	1.200	1.211
(C ₀) ^{1/2} = 0 (negligible)	0.0120	1.183	1.179	1.195
	0.0139	1.175	1.174	1.189
B = 1.47 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.0162	1.167	1.167	1.183
Eqns. (1) to (1c) combined	0.0231	1.153	1.145	1.169
D ₀ = 1.335 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.0547	1.136	1.127	1.172
S _D = 2.78 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.102	1.122	1.130	1.172

^a Refs. 3, 4 and 6. ^b Refs. 4-6. ^c Ref. 3.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF (κ/√a)S OBSERVED AND CALCULATED

Electrolyte used	κ	√a	S × 10 ⁵	Values of (κ/√a)S × 10 ⁻⁵	
				Obs.	Calcd.
LiCl	1.22	2.37	0.622	0.32	0.32
NaCl	1.22	2.35	0.663	0.36	0.344
KCl	1.22	2.34	0.78	0.41	0.407
CsCl	1.22	2.09	0.80	0.47	0.467
CaCl ₂	1.14	2.72	1.808	0.76	0.757
BaCl ₂	1.14	2.92	1.876	0.73	0.733

TABLE 4—VALUES OF B OBSERVED AND CALCULATED BY EQUATION (4a)

Electrolyte used	D ₀ × 10 ⁵	r	h	Values of B × 10 ⁻⁵	
				Obs.	Calcd.
LiCl	1.367	1.03	5.6	0.46	0.49
NaCl	1.611	1.04	4.1	0.30	0.314
KCl	1.994	1.64	3.0	0.26	0.265
CsCl	2.044	2.3	2.4	0.23	0.237
CaCl ₂	1.335	1.35	12.5	1.47	1.47
BaCl ₂	1.336	1.6	10.6	1.14	1.16

those for CaCl₂ and BaCl₂ have been so chosen as to agree with the observed values of B.

Discussion

It appears from the data recorded in the Tables 1 and 2 that the values of D calculated by equation (LL) begin to deviate from the observed results even at as low a concentration as 0.001 M, while

those calculated by using equation (4) agree well with those observed upto a concentration of about 0.1 M. For LiCl, the equation used by Harned and coworkers³ is found to be as satisfactory as equation (4) upto 0.01 M, the highest concentration to which the authors³ applied their equation. For CaCl₂, the equation used by Harned and coworkers^{4,5} yields values of D which are much higher than those observed.

The failure of equation (LL) and that used by Harned and coworkers^{4,5} for CaCl₂ may be attributed mainly to the use of the Debye-Hückel expression in the thermodynamic part and to some minor extent to the use of the electrophoretic effect in the mobility part of equation (1). This inference is supported by the fact that equation (4), which holds good for the data recorded in the Tables 1 and 2, has been derived by modifying the thermodynamic part and neglecting the electrophoretic effect for the electrolytes KCl, CsCl, CaCl₂ and BaCl₂ in the mobility part of equation (1). It may be that the electrophoretic effect is proportional to [(λ₁⁰ - λ₂⁰)/Δ⁰]² and not to [(|Z₂|λ₁⁰ - |Z₁|λ₂⁰)/Δ⁰]² as recorded in equation (1e). If that be the case then for the aforesaid four electrolytes the electrophoretic effect should be negligible since the difference between λ₁⁰ and λ₂⁰ of these electrolytes is small.

It may also be noted that when C is lower than 0.005 M, the following equation should hold good for the 1 : 1 electrolytes used,

$$D = D_0 - (\kappa/\sqrt{a})S (C^{1/2} - C_0^{1/2}) \quad (4b)$$

The values of √a recorded in Table 3 have been found from those of a, collected from papers published previously^{9,15} and they correspond to 25° except that for BaCl₂. For BaCl₂, a has been found to be 8.2 Å from freezing point data for the activity coefficient and corresponds to temperature slightly below 0°. At 25°, it is assumed to be a little higher than 8.2 Å. The value of √a = 2.92 recorded in Table 2 corresponds to a = 8.5 Å, and it justifies the aforesaid assumption. It is to be noted from the data recorded in Table 3 that the observed values of (κ/√a)S agree well with those calculated.

The data recorded in Table 4 show that the agreement between the observed and calculated values of B is satisfactory. The values of r at C = 1 M have been collected from the publication⁶ and those of h for the 1 : 1 electrolytes from the previous publication of the author¹⁵. For the 2 : 1 electrolytes, they are so chosen as to fit the observed values of B. It may be mentioned that the values of h for BaCl₂ and CaCl₂ found by Robinson and Stokes⁹, are 8.4 and 11.9, respectively and those by Miller are 14.0 and 20.9, respectively. The values of h for these two salts recorded in Table 4 thus occupy an intermediate position between the two sets of values mentioned above and may be accepted provisionally.

In conclusion, it may be stated that the Onsager-Fuoss equation as modified by the author and expressed in the form, $D = D_0 - (\alpha/\sqrt{a})S(C^{1/2} - C_0^{1/2}) + BC$, holds good for the electrolytes recorded in Tables 1 and 2 upto a concentration of 0.1 M.

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